

ANALYTICAL MEHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF CILNIDIPINE AND METOPROLOL BY UHPLC IN SOLID DOSAGE FORMS

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Abstract

Literature review reveals that there is no analytical method reported for the analysis of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol by UHPLC in solid dosage form. Spectrophotometer, HPLC and RP-HPLC are the reported analytical methods for compounds either individually or in combination with other dosage form. Hence, it was felt that, there is a need of new analytical method development for the simultaneous estimation of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol by UHPLC in pharmaceutical dosage form. Present work is aimed to develop a new, simple, fast, rapid, accurate, efficient and reproducible Analytical mehod development and validation for the simultaneous estimation of cilnidipine and metoprolol by UHPLC in solid dosage forms. The developed method will be validated according to ICH guidelines. A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Cilnidipine and Metoprolol in solid dosage form. Retention time of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol were found 0.61min and 1.20 min respectively. System precision. %RSD of the Cilnidipine and Metoprolol were found 0.89 and 1.01 respectively. %Assay were obtained as 99.86% for Cilnidipine and 99.39 % for Metoprolol. Regression equation of Cilnidipine is $y = 4.4172x + 1.976$. Regression equation of Metoprolol is $y=64.541x+ 79.588$. Retention times were decreased and that run time was decreased, so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

Key words: Cilnidipine, Metoprolol, method development, validation

Introduction

Analytical chemistry has played a major role in the changes facing the pharmaceutical Industry today. Traditionally viewed as a service organization, the analytical department has become a significant parameter in the drug development process. [1] Indeed, the demand for analytical data has become a critical path activity for selection of molecule for full development. The pharmaceutical analysis plays a major role in assuring, identity, safety, efficacy, purity and quality of drug product the need for pharmaceutical analysis is driven largely by regulatory requirements. [2] Literature review reveals that there is no analytical method reported for the analysis of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol by UHPLC in solid dosage form. Spectrophotometer, HPLC and RP-HPLC are the reported analytical methods for compounds either individually or in combination with other dosage form. [3] Hence, it was felt that, there is a need of new analytical method development for the simultaneous estimation of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol by UHPLC in pharmaceutical dosage form. Present work is aimed to develop a new, simple, fast, rapid, accurate, efficient and reproducible Analytical method development and validation for the simultaneous estimation of cilnidipine and metoprolol by UHPLC in solid dosage forms. The developed method will be validated according to ICH guidelines. [4]

Analytical method development and validation for the simultaneous estimation of cilnidipine and metoprolol by uhplc in solid dosage forms. The Analytical method development and validation for the simultaneous estimation of cilnidipine and metoprolol by uhplc in solid dosage forms and optimizing the chromatographic conditions. The developed method is validated according to ICH guidelines for various parameters specified in ICH guidelines, Q2. [5]

Materials and methods^[6]

Materials:

Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate tablets, HPLC water, Acetonitrile, Methanol, Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate and Ortho-phosphoric acid. All the above chemicals and solvents are from Rankemz

Instruments:

- Electronics Balance-Denver
- p^H meter -BVK enterprises, India
- Ultra sonicator-BVK enterprises
- Agilent technologies 1220 infinity series

- **Serial no:DECAG00308**
- **SOFTWARE: CHEMSTATION_open laz**

Methods:**Chromatographic condition:** ^[7]

1. Column: ZORBAX Eclipse Plus C18; 4.6mm X 50 mm; 1.8 microns
2. Wave length:230nm
3. Flow rate:0.8ml/min
4. Injection volume:2 µl
5. Mobile phase: Mixture of Acetonitrile: Methanol: Buffer in the ratio of 50: 20: 30.
Buffer preparation: 0.5M Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate, pH adjusted to 3.0 with dilute Orthophosphoric acid

Diluent:

Based up on the solubility of the drugs, diluent was selected, mobile phase used as diluent.

Preparation of Standard solution: Weigh accurately and transfer about 50 mg of Cilnidipine and 250 mg of Metoprolol Succinate standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with mobile phase. Dilute 10 ml of this solution to 100 ml with mobile phase.

Preparation of Sample solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 5 mg of Cilnidipine into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase.

Validation: ^[8]

System suitability parameters: The system suitability parameters was determined by preparing standard solution of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol succinate were injected six times and the parameters like peak tailing, resolution and USP plate count were determined. The % RSD for the area of six standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

Specificity: Checking of the interference in the optimized method. We should not find any interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of these drugs in this method. So this method was said to be specific.

Precision: ^[9]

Preparation of standard solution: Weigh accurately and transfer about 50 mg of Cilnidipine and 250 mg of Metoprolol Succinate standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase. Dilute 10 ml of this solution to 100 ml with mobile phase.

Preparation of sample solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 5 mg of Cilnidipine into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase.

Linearity (for Cilnidipine):

Preparation of standard stock solution: Weighed accurately and transferred about 50 mg of Cilnidipine standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask.

50% Cilnidipine Standard solution: 5.0ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 100ml.

75% Cilnidipine Standard solution: 7.5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 100ml.

100% Cilnidipine Standard solution: 10.0ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 100ml.

125% Cilnidipine Standard solution: 12.5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 100ml.

150% Cilnidipine Standard solution: 15.0ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 100ml.

Linearity (for Metoprolol Succinate):^[10]

Preparation of standard stock solution: Weighed accurately and transferred about 250 mg of Metoprolol succinate standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask.

50% Metoprolol succinate Standard solution: 5.0ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 100ml

75% Metoprolol succinate Standard solution: 7.5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 100ml.

100% Metoprolol succinate Standard solution: 10.0ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 100ml

125% Metoprolol succinate Standard solution:12.5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 100ml.

150% Metoprolol succinate Standard solution:15.0ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 100ml.

Accuracy (for Cilnidipine):

Preparation of Standard stock solution: Weighed accurately and transferred about 50 mg of Cilnidipine standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolved and made up to the volume with mobile phase. Diluted 10 ml of this solution to 100 ml with mobile phase. **For**

preparation of 80% solution : Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 4.0 mg of Cilnidipine into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase.

For preparation of 100% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 5 mg of Cilnidipine into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase.

For preparation of 120% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 6.0 mg of Cilnidipine into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase.

Procedure:

The standard solution, Accuracy -80%, Accuracy -100% and Accuracy -120% solutions were injected. The amount found and amount added for Cilnidipine mean recovery values were calculated and the results were summarized.

Accuracy (for Metoprolol succinate):

Preparation of Standard stock solution: Weighed accurately and transferred about 250 mg of Metoprolol succinate standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolved and made up to the volume with mobile phase. Diluted 10 ml of this solution to 100 ml with mobile phase.

For preparation of 80% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 20 mg of Metoprolol succinate into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase.

For preparation of 100% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 25 mg of Metoprolol succinate into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase.

For preparation of 120% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 30 mg of Metoprolol succinate into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and make up to the volume with mobile phase.

Procedure

The standard solution, Accuracy -80%, Accuracy -100% and Accuracy -120% solutions were injected. The amount found and amount added for Metoprolol succinate mean recovery values were calculated and the results were summarized.

Acceptance Criteria:

The % Recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102.0

Robustness: Small deliberate changes in method like Flow rate and Wavelength were made but

there were no recognized change in the result and were within range as per ICH Guide lines. Robustness conditions like Flow minus, Flow plus, Wavelength decreasing and Wavelength increasing was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much effected and all the parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limit.

Results and discussion

Method development: Method development was done by changing various, mobile phase ratios, buffers etc.

Trial 1:

Chromatographic conditions:

Mobile phase	: Acetonitrile : Methanol: Buffer (40:30:30)
Flow rate	: 0.8ml/min
Column	: ZORBAX Eclipse Plus C18; 4.6mm X 50 mm; 1.8 μ
Detector wave length	: 230nm
Injection volume	: 2 μ L
Run time	: 5 min
Diluent	: Mobile phase

Results : improper peak elution and more run time so, further trial is carried out.

Optimized conditions

Chromatographic conditions:

Mobile phase	: Acetonitrile: Methanol: Buffer (50:20:30)
Flow rate	: 0.8ml/min
Column	: ZORBAX Eclipse Plus C18; 4.6mm X 50 mm; 1.8 μ
Detector wave length	: 230nm
Injection volume	: 2 μ L
Run time	: 5 min
Diluent	: Mobile phase

Results : Retention time and peak shape is good.

Observation: Cilnidipine was eluted at 0.61 min and Metoprolol was eluted at 1.20 min with good resolution. Plate count and tailing factor was very satisfactory, so this method was optimized and to be validated.^[11]

System suitability: All the system suitability parameters were within the range and satisfactory as per ICH guidelines.

Figure-1: System suitability Chromatogram

Discussion: According to ICH guidelines plate count should be more than 2000, tailing factor should be less than 2 and resolution must be more than 2. All the system suitable parameters were passed and were within the limits. ^[12]

Specificity:

Table-1: Specificity table for Cilnidipine and Metoprolol

Sample ID	Cilnidipine		Metoprolol	
	RT	AREA	RT	AREA
BLANK	0.61	No peak observed	1.20	No peak observed
STANDARD	0.61	236.532	1.20	274.426
PLACEBO	0.61	No peak observed	1.20	No peak observed

Discussion: Retention time of Cilnidipine was eluted at 0.61min and Retention time of Metoprolol was eluted at 1.20 min. We did not find any interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of these drugs in this method. So this method was said to be specific.

Linearity:

Figure-2: Linearity curves

Discussion: Six linear concentrations of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol were injected in a duplicate manner. Average areas were mentioned above and linearity equations obtained for Cilnidipine was $y = 4.4172x + 1.976$ and Metoprolol was $y = 64.541x + 79.588$. Correlation coefficient obtained was $R^2 = 0.9998$ for the Cilnidipine and $R^2 = 0.9997$ for the Metoprolol respectively. [13]

Table-2: System precision table

Conc. level	Sample ID	Sample wt. (mg)	Sample Area	Calculated Assay (in mg)	Calculated Assay (in percentage)
MIDDLE LEVEL (100%)	Sample -01	75.56	220.563	9.92	99.20
	Sample -02	74.37	219.426	10.03	100.30
	Sample -03	76.28	222.752	9.92	99.20
	Sample -04	75.16	223.853	10.12	101.20
	Sample -05	76.77	223.862	9.91	99.10
	Sample -06	74.94	221.906	10.06	100.60
Average :				9.99	99.93
SD.:				0.09	0.89
%RSD:				0.9	0.89
Conc. level	Sample ID	Sample wt. (mg)	Sample Area	Calculated Assay (in mg)	Calculated Assay (in percentage)
MIDDLE LEVEL (100%)	Sample -01	75.56	275.367	49.56	99.12
	Sample -02	74.37	276.062	50.48	100.96
	Sample -03	76.28	275.984	49.21	98.42
	Sample -04	75.16	273.158	49.43	98.86
	Sample -05	76.77	279.786	49.57	99.14
	Sample -06	74.94	276.862	50.25	100.50
Average :				49.75	99.50
SD.:				0.5	1
%RSD:				1.01	1.01

Discussion: From a single volumetric flask of working standard solution six injections were given and the obtained areas were mentioned above. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD was calculated for Cilnidipine and Metoprolol. % RSD obtained as 0.89% for Cilnidipine and 1.01% for Metoprolol respectively. As the limit of Precision was less than “2” the system precision was passed in this method.

Intermediate precision

Figure-3: Intermediate precision

Discussion: Multiple sampling from a sample stock solution was done and six working sample solutions of same concentrations were prepared, each injection from each working sample solution was given and obtained areas were mentioned in the above table. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD was calculated for Cilnidipine and obtained as 1.17% and % RSD was calculated for Metoprolol and obtained as 1.06%. As the limit of Precision was less than “2” the system precision was passed in this method. ^[14]

Accuracy

Table-3: Accuracy

Conc. Level	Sample ID	qty. spiked. (mg)	Sample Area	Amount Recovered (in percentage)
LOW LEVEL (50%)	Sample -01	8.13	175.863	99.02
	Sample -02	8.02	177.435	101.25
	Sample -03	8.08	175.647	99.50
MIDDLE LEVEL (100%)	Sample -01	10.12	220.453	99.70
	Sample -02	10.04	221.672	101.00
	Sample -03	10.09	219.643	99.60
HIGH LEVEL (150%)	Sample -01	12.07	264.742	100.33
	Sample -02	12.13	263.963	99.59
	Sample -03	12.08	265.384	100.50
Average :				100.05
SD.:				0.75
%RSD:				0.75
Conc. level	Sample ID	qty. spiked. (mg)	Sample Area	Amount Recovered (in percentage)
LOW LEVEL (50%)	Sample -01	40.98	223.453	98.88
	Sample -02	41.26	227.874	100.15
	Sample -03	40.85	226.158	100.39
MIDDLE LEVEL (100%)	Sample -01	50.15	278.853	100.84
	Sample -02	50.32	275.316	99.22
	Sample -03	51.37	281.096	99.24
HIGH LEVEL	Sample -01	60.32	335.533	100.88

(150%)	Sample -02	60.66	331.095	98.98
	Sample -03	61.28	334.547	99.00
			Average :	99.73
			SD.:	0.83
			%RSD:	0.83

Discussion: Three levels of Accuracy samples were prepared by standard addition method. . Triplicate injections were given for each level of accuracy and mean %Recovery was obtained as **99.02%** and 101.25 % for Cilnidipine and 98.88% and 100.88% for Metoprolol.

Robustness

Table-4: Robustness

S.No	Condition	%RSD of Cilnidipine	%RSD of Metoprolol
1	Flow rate (-)	0.89	1.04
2	Flow rate (+)	1.21	0.96
3	Wavelength (-)	0.77	0.79
4	Wavelength (+)	0.68	1.06

Discussion: Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.6ml/min), Flow plus (1.0ml/min), Wavelength minus and Wavelength plus was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limit. ^[15]

Table-5: Summary

PARAMETERS	CILNIDIPINE	METOPROLOL	LIMIT
Linearity: Regression equation (Y=mx+c)	y = 4.4172x + 1.976 (R ² = 0.9998)	y=64.541x+ 79.588 (R ² = 0.9997)	R<1
Assay (% mean assay)	99.86%	99.39 %	90-110%
Specificity	Specific	Specific	No interference of any peak
System precision %RSD	0.89	1.01	NMT 2.0%
Intermediate precision day-01 (%RSD)	1.17%	1.06%.	NMT 2.0%

Intermediate precision day-02 (%RSD)		0.90%	0.59%	NMT 2.0%
Accuracy %		99.02% - 101.25 %	98.88% - 100.88%	98-102%
Robustness	FM	0.89	1.04	%RSD NMT 2.0
	FP	1.21	0.96	
	WM	0.77	0.79	
	WP	0.68	1.06	

Conclusion

A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Cilnidipine and Metoprolol in solid dosage form. Retention time of Cilnidipine and Metoprolol were found 0.61min and 1.20 min respectively. System precision %RSD of the Cilnidipine and Metoprolol were found 0.89 and 1.01 respectively. %Assay were obtained as 99.86% for Cilnidipine and 99.39 % for Metoprolol. Regression equation of Cilnidipine is $y = 4.4172x + 1.976$. Regression equation of Metoprolol is $y = 64.541x + 79.588$. Retention times were decreased and that run time was decreased, so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

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